

**SOY PROCESSING PRODUCTS AND THEIR NUTRITIONAL
IMPORTANCE**

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**SOYANI QAYTA QILISH MAHSULOTLARI VA ULARNING
OZIQLIK AHAMIYATI**

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**ПРОДУКТЫ ПЕРЕРАБОТКИ СОИ И ИХ ПИЩЕВАЯ
ЦЕННОСТЬ**

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Abstract: *Nowadays, soy is one of the most important crops in agriculture and the food industry. Various products are obtained through soy processing, and these products are of great significance for human health. Soy-derived products have high nutritional value, containing proteins, fats, vitamins, and minerals. This thesis provides detailed information about soy processing products and their nutritional importance.*

Keywords: *Rhizobium, soy, soy products, soy flour, soy oil, processing.*

Annotatsiya: *Hozirgi vaqtda soya qishloq xo'jaligi va oziq-ovqat sanoatida eng muhim ekinlardan biridir. Soyani qayta ishlash orqali turli mahsulotlar olinadi*

va bu mahsulotlar inson salomatligi uchun katta ahamiyatga ega. Soyadan olingan mahsulotlar oqsillar, yog'lar, vitaminlar va minerallarni o'z ichiga olgan yuqori oziqaviy qiymatga ega. Ushbu tezisda soyani qayta ishlash mahsulotlari va ularning oziqaviy ahamiyati haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: *Rizobium, soya, soya mahsulotlari, soya uni, soya yog'i, qayta ishlash*

Аннотация: *В настоящее время соя является одной из важнейших культур в сельском хозяйстве и пищевой промышленности. В результате переработки сои получают различные продукты, имеющие большое значение для здоровья человека. Продукты, полученные из сои, обладают высокой пищевой ценностью, содержат белки, жиры, витамины и минералы. В данной диссертации представлена подробная информация о продуктах переработки сои и их пищевой ценности.*

Ключевые слова: *Rhizobium, соя, соевые продукты, соевая мука, соевое масло, переработка*

Introdiksiyon

Soy (*Glycine max*) is one of the most important leguminous crops in the world, widely used in the food industry, animal husbandry, and technological product manufacturing. Due to its high content of proteins, fats, carbohydrates, and essential micronutrients, soy plays a crucial role in human nutrition as well as in animal feed [1,3].

Historically, soy has been cultivated in Southeast Asian countries such as China, India, Japan, Korea, Vietnam, and Indonesia. Due to its adaptability, soy has expanded beyond its original regions and is now grown in more than sixty countries worldwide [5].

Soy is highly valued not only in Japan, China, and Southeast Asian countries but also in America and Canada, where people prioritize their health. According to researchers, soy is not only delicious and beneficial but also a powerful agent against cancer. It has been found that soy contains phytochemical compounds that have anti-tumor and anti-sclerosis effects. Soybean oil and animal fats are comparable in terms of both quantity and amino acid composition. Soy proteins are highly digestible, with an absorption rate reaching up to 70%.

Research Methodology

Soy is not just a protein source; it also contains essential minerals such as potassium, sodium, calcium, iron, and zinc, as well as vitamins from the B and C groups. Soy products are distinguished by the absence of cholesterol and partially unsaturated fatty acids, along with their low caloric content. Furthermore, the dietary

fiber present in soy products makes them comparable to strawberries (4%). In this regard, soy is second only to raspberries (5%) and is considered one of the leading plant-based products [2].

The great scholar Avicenna (Abu Ali ibn Sina) described soy as a plant that "ensures health and longevity." It is not only nourishing but also has medicinal properties. Ancient texts dating back over a thousand years refer to this plant as "sacred soy." It helps treat various diseases and is a dietary product beneficial for people of all ages, including children, the elderly, men, and women.

Soybeans, due to their high protein, fat, and beneficial microelement content, serve as a valuable raw material in the food industry, pharmaceuticals, and animal husbandry. Various products derived from soy processing include soybean oil, soy flour, soy protein, soy meat, soy milk, and fermented products [2,4].

Analysis and results

Soy is an annual leguminous plant whose roots contain Rhizobium bacteria. These bacteria help improve soil fertility by fixing atmospheric nitrogen. Therefore, soy is cultivated as a crop that enhances soil quality [2].

Table 1.

Various products derived from soybean processing:

Product	Processing Method	Application Area
Soybean oil	Pressing or extraction	Food, cosmetics, biodiesel
Soy flour	Oil extraction and grinding	Bakery products, animal feed
Soy protein	Protein extraction and drying	Sports nutrition, healthy diets
Soy meat	Structural modification through extrusion	Vegetarian products
Soy milk	Grinding soybeans and extracting liquid	Dairy substitute
Fermented products	Fermentation using bacteria	Soy sauce, miso, tempeh

One of the most nutritionally valuable soy processing products is soybean oil, which has become widely used today. The production of this oil constitutes approximately 9% of the total vegetable oil production in our country. In addition to oil, soybeans contain proteins (30-50%) and phosphatides (0.55-0.60%), which are used for food and feed purposes due to their high biological value.

Soybean oil is extracted through two primary methods:

- **Mechanical:** Crushing and pressing the raw material to extract the oil.
- **Chemical:** Treating specially prepared raw material with organic solvents and gradually extracting the oil. Initially, about 80% of the oil is extracted through pressing, followed by extraction to obtain the remaining oil. In direct extraction, soybean oil is obtained in a single step [1,2,3].

Table 2.

Quality characteristics of raw soybean oil:

Characteristic	Description
Aroma & Smell	Characteristic soybean oil odor, no unusual smell
Color	Natural, greenish-brown
Transparency	Slightly cloudy, possible sediment
Non-fat content (%)	≤ 0.2
Moisture content (%)	0.36
Acid value (mg KOH/g)	4.00
Peroxide value (½ mol/kg)	≤ 5.00
Phosphatide content (%)	≤ 4.00
Iodine value	≤ 100

Direct extraction is a modern method that simplifies the technological process of oil production by eliminating the pressing step. The refining process removes various impurities while preserving beneficial components such as fat-soluble vitamins (K, E), carotenoids, sterols, polyunsaturated fatty acids, and biologically active substances.

Refining methods are categorized as mechanical, physical, and physicochemical (sedimentation, filtration, centrifugation, hydration, alkali refining, bleaching, deodorization).

Table 3.

Quality characteristics of refined soybean oil:

Characteristic	Description
Aroma & Smell	No odor, tasteless
Color	Light yellow
Transparency	Transparent
Non-fat content (%)	None
Moisture content (%)	0.1
Acid value (mg KOH/g)	0.3

Peroxide value ($\frac{1}{2}$ mol/kg)	≤ 5.00
Phosphatide content (%)	≤ 0.05
Iodine value	≤ 12

The by-products of oil extraction, such as meal (from pressing) and cake (from extraction), are valuable protein sources used in food and animal feed.

Conclusion

Soybean oil is highly beneficial in cosmetics, especially for normal and dry skin. It nourishes, moisturizes, and forms a protective barrier that retains moisture. Soy oil-based masks rejuvenate, smooth, and enhance skin health, restoring elasticity and tone. Regular consumption of refined soybean oil ensures optimal vitamin E absorption, contributing to overall well-being. Refined soybean oil is excellent for frying fish and meat, baking, and preparing soups, main dishes, and salads. However, in our region, soybean oil is not widely used due to lack of familiarity. In contrast, in East Asia, where soy is a staple, it is the primary oil, while other oils are secondary. For optimal preservation, refined soybean oil should be stored in glass containers in dark places.

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